

As on 01-04-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended in order to make record of the crop's native origin into the knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several sources mentioning of the crops. The sources may be review papers, databases and web articles. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken. The suggested keyword is “scientific name” + “origin”.
2. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. There are four fields to be entered, three of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records.

1.2 Location (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the location where the crop is initially originated
- To create a new record, one **MUST** ensure there is no previous record of the crop at the same location to avoid repetitive record

1.3 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the native origin of the crop itself.

1.4 Metadata ID

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in ‘Metadata’ table before entering Metadata ID